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OPENNESS OF UZBEK FINANCIAL MARKET TO FOREIGN INVESTORS: PROBLEMS AND PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract. *This thesis investigates the openness of Uzbekistan's financial market to foreign investors, a crucial aspect of the country's economic policy in the context of a rapidly evolving global economic landscape. It aims to analyze the current state of market openness, identify existing barriers to foreign investment, and explore potential avenues for future development. By examining the effects of market openness on Uzbekistan's economic growth, this study provides insights into how enhanced accessibility for foreign investors could influence the national economy. The research underscores the importance of foreign capital, which not only augments investment volumes but also facilitates the transfer of technology, expertise, and managerial skills, thereby stimulating economic growth and enhancing the nation's competitiveness.*

Keywords: *financial market openness, foreign investors, economic policy, global economic landscape, economic growth, foreign investment barriers, market development, foreign capital, technology transfer, managerial skills, national competitiveness, theoretical analysis, empirical data, investment recommendations*

ОТКРЫТОСТЬ ФИНАНСОВОГО РЫНКА УЗБЕКИСТАНА ДЛЯ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ИНВЕСТОРОВ: ПРОБЛЕМЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ

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Абстракт. *В данной диссертации исследуется открытость финансового рынка Узбекистана для иностранных инвесторов, что является важнейшим аспектом экономической политики страны в контексте быстро меняющегося глобального экономического ландшафта. Целью проекта является анализ текущего состояния открытости рынка, выявление существующих барьеров для иностранных инвестиций и изучение потенциальных путей будущего развития. Изучая влияние открытости рынка на экономический рост Узбекистана, данное исследование дает представление о том, как расширение доступности для иностранных инвесторов может повлиять на национальную экономику. Исследование подчеркивает важность иностранного капитала, который не только увеличивает объемы инвестиций, но и способствует передаче технологий, опыта и управленческих навыков, тем самым стимулируя экономический рост и повышая конкурентоспособность страны.*

Ключевые слова: *открытость финансового рынка, иностранные инвесторы, экономическая политика, глобальный экономический ландшафт, экономический рост, барьеры для иностранных инвестиций, развитие рынка, иностранный капитал, трансфер технологий, управленческие навыки, национальная конкурентоспособность, теоретический анализ, эмпирические данные, инвестиционные рекомендации.*

The openness of the financial market to foreign investors is a key aspect of economic policy for many countries, including Uzbekistan. This issue remains pertinent in the rapidly changing global economic landscape as countries seek new sources of economic growth. This thesis aims to analyze the current degree of openness of the Uzbek financial market to foreign investors, identify the challenges hindering this process, and outline prospects for its development. Examining this topic will allow for an assessment of the impact of market openness on Uzbekistan's economic development and offer recommendations for overcoming potential obstacles.

The financial market is considered open when it provides broad access to foreign investors to various financial instruments and investment opportunities. This means that foreign investors have the ability to freely purchase, sell, and trade securities, currencies, commodity contracts, and other assets on the market, without significant restrictions or obstacles.

Attracting foreign investors plays a crucial role in the development of the Uzbekistan economy. Foreign capital investments contribute not only to increasing the volume of investments in various sectors but also to the transfer of technologies, expertise, and managerial skills. This can stimulate economic growth, enhance productivity, and improve the competitiveness of the Uzbek economy.

Uzbekistan's economy continued to grow at a healthy rate with GDP rising to \$86,1 billion in 2023, or 6% in real terms. The greatest contribution to economic growth was made by the service sector (2.6%) and industry (1.5%). Following them are agriculture (1%), net taxes on products (0.5%), and construction (0.4%). According to statistics, the trade, transport, and IT sectors showed the most active growth, increasing by more than 10%. The lowest growth rates were observed in agriculture, forestry, and fisheries (4.1%). The government did not publish private external debt data. Higher food, energy and logistics costs caused by the Russian invasion of Ukraine resulted in 8.77% (12.3 % in 2022) inflation in Uzbekistan. The Central Bank raised the key interest rate from 14% to 17% in March 2022 and then cut it back to 15% in July 2022 and to 14% in March 2023 as the negative impact of the Russia-Ukraine war on Uzbekistan's economy was milder than expected and remittances to Uzbekistan surged by 2.1 times to \$16.9 billion in 2022. The remittances include not only the earnings of Uzbek labor migrants

abroad, but also comprised financial transfers by Russian citizens who relocated, some temporarily and some permanently, to Uzbekistan.

In 2021, direct foreign investments amounted to \$8.6 billion. This is 30% more than in 2020 (\$6.6 billion) and 14.6% more than the expected amount for 2021 (\$7.5 billion). According to the report of the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD), Uzbekistan attracted a record \$2.5 billion in direct foreign investments in 2022.

In 2022, the volume of foreign direct investments worldwide decreased by 12.4% to \$1.3 trillion. This was caused by the armed conflict in Ukraine, high prices for food and energy resources, recession risks, and the debt burden in many countries. Despite the fact that negative factors have somewhat weakened, they have not completely disappeared, as there is still high geopolitical tension.

In 2023, the volume of foreign direct investment in Uzbekistan decreased by 16% — from \$2.6 billion to \$2.2 billion. The deficit of the current account relative to GDP reached a historical maximum of \$7.8 billion.

— Direct Investments" in billions.

— Share of Direct Investments relative to GDP" as a percentage.

Bar Chart (Blue): Represents the volume of direct investments in billions. It shows the annual direct investments made over the years. The values start low in 2018, rise sharply by 2019, fluctuate in the following years, and then show a slight decline by 2023.

Line Graph (Red): Illustrates the share of direct investments relative to the GDP, expressed in percentages. This line peaks in 2019, indicating the highest proportion of direct investments to GDP, and generally trends downward through 2023.

Measures to stimulate foreign direct investment include improving the investment climate, such as reducing bureaucratic barriers and simplifying registration and licensing procedures. Attracting foreign investors is also crucial, and to this end, events are held to present investment opportunities in Uzbekistan at the international level. Additionally, stimulating investment in key sectors of the economy through incentives and tax preferences can play a significant role in attracting more investment.

Managing the current account deficit requires the development of export-import operations and the promotion of exports of goods and services. Diversification of trading partners to reduce dependence on individual markets is also important. Moreover, attracting foreign investment can help strengthen currency reserves and improve the balance of payments. Future forecasts anticipate sustained growth in foreign direct investment due to improvements in the investment climate and economic reforms. Stabilization of the current account deficit through export development and investment attraction is also expected to contribute to overall improvements in Uzbekistan's external trade. In the long term, improving the investment climate and implementing further economic reforms will attract more investment and accelerate the country's economic development.

In conclusion, the prospects for the development of Uzbekistan's economy are closely tied to its ability to attract foreign direct investment and manage its current account deficit effectively. Despite a decrease in foreign direct investment in 2023, there remain opportunities for growth through continued efforts to improve the investment climate, diversify trading partners, and implement targeted policies to stimulate investment in key sectors. By addressing these challenges and capitalizing on its economic potential, Uzbekistan can position itself for sustainable growth and prosperity in the future. However, it will require concerted efforts from both the government and private sector to realize these objectives and navigate the evolving global economic landscape successfully.

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